

3rd Annual Conference of the EuroXanth COST Action
Faculty of Horticulture, Lednice, Czech Republic
9–11 September 2019

Unravelling the role of mineral elements in olive response to *Xylella fastidiosa* infections

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Keywords: *Xylella fastidiosa*, olive resistance, ionome remodelling, ICP-OES

The plant vascular system is the route of transport of mineral elements that play key roles in controlling a multitude of metabolic functions. The xylem colonizer *Xylella fastidiosa*, like any other endophyte, has enacted a series of strategies to compete with the host for mineral ions, and ensure its growth. Many of the strategies are linked to the regulation of virulence traits. Previous studies showed that remodelling of leaf ionome occurs during *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* and *multiplex* infection, uncovering the existence of a mineral element-based response during host-pathogen interaction.

X. fastidiosa subsp. *pauca* is severely affecting olives in Apulia, so to identify possible mechanisms of resistance we investigated whether the mineral elements play a role in OQDS progress and in the differential responses shown by resistant ('Leccino') and susceptible ('Ogliarola salentina') cultivars.

Leaf ionome of symptomatic and asymptomatic samples collected in two fields in the infected area was determined by Inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry. Data showed that 'Leccino' maintains consistently higher Mn concentrations than 'Ogliarola salentina', independent of disease status. Given the prominent role of Mn in plant enzymes, we hypothesized that the increased availability of this element may provide a basis for 'Leccino' resistance by activating antioxidant enzymes and counterbalancing the uptake of transition metals, triggered by the pathogen. 'Leccino' also showed a significant increase in Ca levels as reported before for other *X. fastidiosa* hosts, in response to the progress of symptoms. This Ca increase was not detected in 'Ogliarola salentina', probably due to the advanced stage of symptomatology evidenced in the field. Previous data suggested that the levels of increased Ca were correlated to severity of disease, therefore,

understanding how 'Leccino' is able to withstand the activation of a *X. fastidiosa*-induced cascade driven by Ca increase, may help further our knowledge of the disease progression in other hosts.

Acknowledgements

This work was done in the framework of an STM granted by the EU COST Action CA16107 and with the financial and scientific support of the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N. 635646 "Pest Organisms Threatening Europe POnTE" and N. 727987 "*Xylella fastidiosa* Active Containment Through a multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy XF-ACTORS".